

8T – Curvature Knots

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primorial coupling constants series under shifting the net variation, i.e. net curvature from a prime number to an odd number, which could be the result of two primes, multiplied. We can predict a curvature knot, which can not vanish into matter but also cannot propagate as a bosonic field. The result is a knot of curvature, time invariant on the matric tensor.

Introduction

The new 8T framework regard bosons as net curvature on the matric tensor. The net curvature are of discrete amounts and is isomorphic to the prime numbers or one. The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $M = M_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The coupling constants series is described in equations (1) to (1.2):

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_{R\#} = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

Reader can vividly see the importance of the prime numbers to this series. However, as was demonstrated in the 8T thesis, there could be variations of the value of the N_V values, given an invoked conservation law of curvature. Concerning the N_V there is a certain degree of flexibility, which is going to be expended in this paper.

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_1 + 1 \quad (1.3)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1 \quad (1.31)$$

Suppose that instead of a prime number as in equations (1.3) and (1.31) describing the weak and the electric, we would have a number that is odd, which could be a composite of odd number primes. Define the odd number function:

$$\Phi_n = 2n + 1 \quad (2)$$

$$n \in \mathbb{R}; \Phi_n \notin \mathbb{P}$$

$\mathbb{P} \rightarrow$ set of primes

So Φ_n is a series of odd numbers that replace only the external N_V in the coupling constant series. The new series is now described by:

$$\left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \Phi_{n1} \quad (2.1)$$

$$\left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \Phi_{n2} \quad (2.11)$$

Since Φ_n is not a prime it cannot act as a bosonic ripple field on the matric tensor. Since it is on an even number, divisor of modulo (6) it cannot vanish into matter. It is a composite of prime, or a composite of net curvature, and because it is a composite, which is stable on the matric tensor, we will have a curvature which is time- invariant, not matter like nor boson like. In other words, a knot. The main point is if one is correct, a knot is composite of net curvature, associated with odd numbers. That is an expansion of the 8T, which did not analyze the odd numbers, but rather referred only to prime numbers and even numbers, isomorphic to primes and evens respectively. Since odds are not on the prime critical line the expressions on terms (2.1) and (2.11) would not have spin one, but neither spin one-half, that is to say they cannot be associated with a particle of any sort. According to the size of the odd numbers we should be able to observe those knots on the matric tensor. Below an example to such knot.

References

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